

ORGANIC PESTICIDES. PART IV. SYNTHESIS OF CERTAIN FLUORO-HYDROXYKETONES AND THEIR ALLYL ETHERS

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For studying pesticidal activity, a dozen fluorohydroxyketones have been synthesised by the Fries rearrangement of esters of *p*-fluorophenol, and six of them have been converted into their allyl ethers.

Hydroxyketones and their allyl ethers are well known as contact insecticides in view of their having a combination of toxic and lipoid-soluble groupings in the molecule (Lauger *et al.*, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1944, 27, 918). Recently Buu-Hoi *et al.* (*J. Org. Chem.*, 1953, 18, 910; 1954, 19, 1617) have reported the synthesis of certain fluorohydroxyketones exhibiting biologically interesting properties.

Keeping these observations in view, we have now prepared fluorohydroxyketones and fluoro-allyl ethers as potential pesticides. Twelve esters of *p*-fluorophenol were obtained by the action of the appropriate acid chloride on the phenol. These esters were subjected to the Fries rearrangement at 130° without a solvent. In all cases, *o*-hydroxyketones were obtained responding to Pyman's test (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 280). Six of these hydroxyketones were converted into their allyl ethers.

EXPERIMENTAL

Esters

p-Fluorophenol was prepared by following the method of English *et al.* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 62, 350).

Twelve new esters of *p*-fluorophenol were prepared by heating for 2 hours a reaction mixture of the appropriate acid chloride (0.1 *M*), *p*-fluorophenol (0.1 *M*), anhydrous benzene (25 c.c.), and Mg ribbon (1.2 g.). After cooling, the benzene was distilled off and the residue taken into ether. The ethereal layer was washed with 1% NaOH solution and water, dried, the ether removed, and the residual product either distilled under reduced pressure or alternatively recrystallised from aqueous ethanol. The following esters have been obtained.

TABLE I
Esters of p-fluorophenol.

Sl. No.	1-Hydroxy-4-fluorophenyl esters.	%Yield.	B.P. or M.P.	Formula.	% Carbon.		% Hydrogen.	
					Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
1.	Monochloroacetate	57.8	177°/10mm	C ₆ H ₅ O ₂ ClF	51.16	50.92	3.32	3.18
2.	<i>α</i> -Chloropropionate	62.8	185°/15	C ₈ H ₇ O ₂ ClF	53.32	53.59	4.20	3.97
3.	<i>α</i> -Crotonate	70.0	155-60°/5	C ₁₀ H ₉ O ₂ F	66.38	66.66	4.80	5.00
4.	Caproate ^a	67.3	140°/2	C ₁₂ H ₁₅ O ₂ F	68.19	68.57	6.97	7.14
5.	<i>o</i> -Chlorobenzoate	88.0	182°/30	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ O ₂ ClF	62.52	62.27	3.32	3.15
6.	<i>p</i> -Fluorobenzoate	88.4	77°	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₂ F ₂	66.46	66.66	3.24	3.41
7.	<i>m</i> -Methylbenzoate	97.3	185-90°/17	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ O ₂ F	73.28	73.04	4.63	4.78
8.	<i>p</i> -Methoxybenzoate	79.4	57°	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ O ₃ F	68.44	68.29	4.23	4.47
9.	Caprylate ^a	85.9	165°/17	C ₁₄ H ₁₉ O ₂ F	70.29	70.58	8.19	7.98
10.	Cinnamate	95.8	67°	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ O ₂ F	74.08	74.38	4.32	4.54
11.	Caprate ^a	78.2	167°/12	C ₁₆ H ₂₃ O ₂ F	73.36	72.18	8.46	8.64
12.	Laurate	86.7	205°/20	C ₁₈ H ₃₇ O ₂ F	73.19	73.46	9.32	9.18

Fries Rearrangement of the Esters.—The rearrangement was carried out by heating the ester (0.06*M*) and anhydrous aluminium chloride (0.1*M*) for 2 hours at 130° (Sen and Tewari, this *Journal*, 1952, 29, 421). The *o*-hydroxyketones were isolated and purified in the usual manner, and characterised through their 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazones. Analytical data, m.p., b.p., and yields of the compounds synthesised are recorded in Table II.

TABLE II

† Ketones.	% Yield.	B.P. or M.P.	Fluorohydroxy ketones*.				2:4-Dinitrophenylhydrazones.				
			%Carbon. Found.	%Carbon. Calc.	%Hydrogen. Found.	%Hydrogen. Calc.	M.P.	Formula.	%Nitrogen. Found.	%Nitrogen. Calc.	
1. R-chloro-methyl-K	50.0	177°/10mm	51.13	50.92	3.32	3.18	160°	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₄ ClF	14.83	15.11	
2. R- <i>o</i> -chloro-ethyl-K	50.0	185°/5	53.36	53.59	3.80	3.97	170°	C ₁₂ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₄ ClF	14.21	14.60	
3. R-propenyl-K	20.0	71	66.35	66.66	5.18	5.00	150°	C ₁₀ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₄ F	15.32	15.47	
4. R-amyln-K	87.5	31	68.23	68.57	7.32	7.14	176°	C ₁₂ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₄ F	14.40	14.36	
5. R- <i>o</i> -chloro-phenyl-K	95.8	65°	62.40	62.27	2.97	3.15	178°	C ₁₂ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₄ ClF	12.44	12.94	
6. R- <i>p</i> -fluoro-phenyl-K	83.3	205°/30	66.95	66.66	3.18	3.41	210°	C ₁₂ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₄ F ₂	13.15	13.46	
7. R- <i>m</i> -tolyl-K	92.8	185°/15	72.83	73.04	4.59	4.78	233°	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ O ₂ N ₄ F	13.14	13.59	
8. R- <i>p</i> -methoxy-phenyl-K	60.0	260°/30	68.50	68.29	4.29	4.47	211°	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ O ₄ N ₄ F	12.77	13.08	
9. R-heptyln-K	95.0	47	70.36	70.58	8.21	7.98	141°	C ₂₀ H ₂₂ O ₂ N ₄ F	12.74	13.31	
10. R-styryl-K	52.4	185-90°/20-25	74.58	74.38	4.29	4.54	175°	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ O ₂ N ₄ F	13.16	13.20	
11. R-nonyln-K	55.5	270°/5	72.46	72.18	8.56	8.64	98°	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ O ₂ N ₄ F	12.29	12.50	
12. R-undecyl ⁿ -K	50.0	320°/10	73.19	73.46	9.35	9.18	105°	C ₂₄ H ₂₄ O ₂ N ₄ F	11.50	11.76	

N.B. The esters correspond to those listed in Table I.

* The M.W. of the ketones are the same as that of the respective esters from which they have been prepared by the Fries migration.

† R = 5-fluoro-2-hydroxyphenyl; K = ketone.

Allyl-aryl Ethers

A mixture of allyl bromide (0.11 *M*), freshly fused potassium carbonate (0.15 *M*), *o*-hydroxyketone (0.1 *M*), and dry acetone (100 c.c.) was refluxed on a steam bath for 8-10 hours. After cooling and adding water, the oily layer separating was taken in ether, purified by repeated washings with 10% NaOH solution and water, dried, the ether removed, and the residual liquid distilled under reduced pressure. The allyl ethers obtained are listed in Table III.

TABLE III

Allyl ethers.

<i>o</i> -Hydroxyketones.	*Ethers.	%Yield.	B.P.	Formula.	% Carbon.		% Hydrogen.	
					Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
1. R-propenyl-K	R'-propenyl-K	98.1	190°/10mm	C ₁₂ H ₁₂ O ₂ F	70.63	70.90	6.18	5.90
2. R-amyln-K	R'-amyln-K	84.0	185°/25	C ₁₂ H ₁₄ O ₂ F	72.28	72.00	7.38	7.60
3. R- <i>o</i> -chlorophenyl-K	R'- <i>o</i> -chlorophenyl-K	86.2	215°/25	C ₁₂ H ₁₂ O ₂ ClF	65.86	66.09	3.88	4.13
4. R- <i>p</i> -fluorophenyl-K	R'- <i>p</i> -fluorophenyl-K	99.1	170°/40	C ₁₂ H ₁₂ O ₂ F ₂	81.78	82.05	4.98	5.12
5. R-heptyln-K	R'-heptyln-K	68.6	190°/15	C ₁₇ H ₂₀ O ₂ F	73.09	73.38	8.03	8.27
6. R-styryl-K	R'-styryl-K	68.5	220°/12	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ O ₂ F	76.29	76.56	5.16	5.31

N.B. K = ketone.

R = 5-fluoro-2-hydroxyphenyl.

R' = 1-allyloxy-4-fluorophenyl.

The pesticidal activity of these compounds is under investigation and will be communicated in due course.

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